

**Socio-Economic Essence of Modern Concepts of Tourism Development in the Surkhandarya
Region**

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Abstract. *Tourism, with its multifaceted composition, has an active influence on all spheres of public life. It makes it possible to develop many aspects of the economy. Including transportation networks, communications, road construction, hotels, catering establishments, communal economy, domestic services, service sector, trade networks, etc.K. The development of Tourism May at the same time cover a number of areas related to the provision of quality services to tourists, establishing a unique industry of recreation, hordiq release, Entertainment masks.*

Keywords: *tourists, tourism, guests, ecological tourism, recreation.*

INTRODUCTION

The tourism sector is currently one of the most productive in the world, and its share in the economy is growing. Therefore, many countries are developing the tourism industry. In particular, special attention is paid to the development of this industry in our country.

Uzbekistan has a rich tourist potential and all opportunities for the development of tourism, thanks to which various measures for the development of the tourism sector in our country, decisions and decrees of our president are being developed. President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh.M.The decree of Mirziyoev dated February 3, 2018 "on the creation of favorable conditions for the development of tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated PF-5326, February 6, 2018 "on the creation of favorable conditions for the development of tourism potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan"dated PF-3509 and "on further improvement of tourism development activities of the state property Committee" dated PF-3510, Decree of February 7, 2018 "on measures for the rapid development of domestic tourism"PF-3514, decree of January 5, 2019 "on additional measures for the rapid development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan"PF-5611", decree of May 28, 2020"PF-6002" on measures to reduce the negative impact of the coronavirus pandemic " on the provision of non-delay measures to, The decree of June 19, 2020 PF-4755 "on additional measures for the development of the tourism sector in accordance with the requirements of the enhanced regime of sanitary and epidemiological security", PF-6165 of February 9, 2021 "on measures for the further development of domestic and pilgrimage tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan"are among them.

The beautiful and unique nature of our country, which includes hundreds of historical monuments, mountains, steppes and deserts, the spiritual and ethnic heritage of the International Living in our country attract peoples living in different parts of the world to Uzbekistan. Due to this, the development of Tourism Sox in the cross-section of mintakas in our country is among the most important issues, such as improving the socio-economic mechanisms for the development of mintakas, beating their problems and shortcomings, determining the priority junctions of their development, improving the socio-economic mechanisms of the development of mintakas tourism.

Currently, the problem with the development and management of Tourism consists in adapting it to international standards, developing programs for the development of tourism, which are one of the main directions of management and development, effective planning, studying foreign experiences in the organization of the activities of tourist enterprises and developing mechanisms for their use in the conditions of our country.

The economic and social task of Tourism Development is that it contributes to the development of the types of activities that work in cooperation with tourism in the regions, to increase the level and quality of living of the population of the region, and to the development of the socio-economic infrastructure of the region.

It is worth noting that the sustainable development of the tourism sector in mintakas, in addition to direct revenues to GDP, increases the profitability of closely interconnected industries, while meeting the secondary demand for goods and services.

Tourism markets require labor to hotelier and catering enterprises, sanatorium-resort networks, as well as other areas of tourism activity. Thanks to this, tourism activities promote the employment of the population. 100 jobs created in the field of tourism, according to the all-around Tourism Organization, will cause the creation of 150 jobs in other areas. According to the opinions of researchers conducting research in this field, 1 job created in the field can be arranged up to 7 jobs in other related fields. Including sales, placement, feeding, transportation, banking, insurance, medical services, etc.

In tourism markets, the processes of import, as well as export of tourist goods and services are carried out. In the process of importing tourist goods and services, in the active second case of the economy of this country, there is talk of a passive type. One of the peculiarities of the network is that tourist goods and services are not excluded in exports, but are consumed in the country itself, which receives tourists.

Tourism has a positive effect on small business enterprises operating in the regions, creates conditions for the development of local infrastructure and increases the income of the population. Boshka makes it possible to create a service network in connection with the activities of the network and industries, accelerate their development and diversify the economy.

Tourism makes it possible to redistribute National profits to regions and countries specializing in this area. The development of tourism provides for a high-rate economic growth of regions with a large number of remote populations and a low-growing industry but with its nature, historical-cultural objects.

Attracting investments ensures a dynamic development of Tourism and a fast and high level of utility of the funds spent. It is these elements that form the main resource base of tourism, increasing the originality and attractiveness of the quality of tourist services.

Surkhandarya region has long attracted tourists with its favorable geographical position and natural conditions. The history of this land is considered not only the history of some people, but also an integral part of the peoples of the history of jaxondai. The passage of the Great Silk Road through this country was the basis for the formation of different cultures at different times and served as the basis for the intersection of cultures.

In 2001, Boysun was recognized by UNESCO as a "masterpiece of oral intangible cultural me'ros" with its unique cultural traditions, national costumes, folk oral creativity, thirst tones. The open folkloric festival "Boysun spring", which is held annually ananically, has provided a solid foundation for the confident entry of Surkhandarya region into the Jahan tourism market.

Surkhandarya region has more than 561 cultural me'ros sites covering the period from the poleolithic to the 20th century. Of these, 444 are archaeological, 36 are architectural and sacred monuments, 39 are monumental and Art Monuments, and 42 are landmarks. These unique tourist resources are mainly located in the old Termez and Sherabad districts, and such monuments are also abundant in other districts of the province. In addition, the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.At the initiative of Mirziyoev, 5.5 hectares of land were allocated from Termez in order to perpetuate the memory of the late Japanese scientist Kato Kyudzo.

The total area of the region is 24,554, and this region has not only a rich-historical region, but also beautiful and unique flora and fauna. In particular, interest in the nature of the Surkhandarya State Reserve is growing not only in the inhabitants of our country, but also in foreign tourists. The Reserve is rich in plant species, with over 600 plant species in the area. More than 20 plant species are unique and protected and are listed in the Red Book. Tubergan Tulip, Surkhan Tulip, Anzur onion, snake onion, red ground astragala, Boysun astragala and other plants are among them. In particular, special attention is paid by international conservation organizations, UN TD and GEF to the preservation and reproduction of biodiversity in the Kohitang mountain, in which it is planned to carry out international projects. The telefilm" in the footsteps of the Tomb "about a rare and endangered species of hyacinth – a stork or horned goat-was filmed by the studio" uzbektelegfilm " and shown several times on Republican television.

In the Surkhandarya region as a whole, the tourism sector has a positive impact on the region's economy, serving as the main catalyst for their economic growth.

We believe that it is advisable to carry out the following work on the sustainable development of tourism in the region in chikkan Khol, to bring it to new stages, increase its share in GDP and improve the quality of services:

- to attract the local community and the local economy to the planning and development of tourist activities on a regional scale, to overcome the difficulties associated with the Tax, Customs Service and preventing the development of other tourism;
- Tourist enterprises operating in surkhandarya region improve the system of professional qualification of employees, analyze the region with their own tourist resources , further accelerate the development of a program of specific measures for the development of the industry and strengthen control over their implementation;

- implementation of marketing activities for the release of national tourist products to the tourism market of chalcara, the creation of national and attractive tourist products, as well as improving the use of marketing Research;
- to prepare personnel suitable for state programs for the industry and meeting the requirements of today, to establish the exchange of international experiences in order to improve their knowledge and skills, etc.q.

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